

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Abdujabborova Madinabonu G'ulomjon qizi

THE CONCEPT OF TRANSLATION METHODS AND TRANSLATION

PROBLEMS OF MOVIE TRANSLATION

DRJI

Universal
Impact Factor

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

zenodo

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

2023-2024

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ